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ECOLOGICAL SUSTAINABILITY AND XENOBIOTIC POLLUTANT DEGRADATION

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ABSTRACT

Microorganisms can survive in a toxic environment by utilising carbon, phosphorous, sulfur, and nitrogen from the available sources thanks to their ability to detoxify xenobiotic substances. The most practical and efficient metabolic method for breaking down xenobiotic substances is biotransformation. Because of specific genes, enzymes, and degradative systems, microorganisms possess extraordinary abilities. Due to their special characteristics, microorganisms like bacteria and fungus can either fully or partially metabolize xenobiotic compounds in a variety of habitats. The molecular mechanisms of degradative processes and the routes to decontaminate or alter the fundamental structure of xenobiotics in nature can be understood using a variety of state-of-the-art techniques. These techniques look at new proteins, catabolic genes, and microbes along with their metabolic apparatus. In order to identify the catabolic genes, enzymes, and strategies involved in employing an environmentally friendly strategy to counter the threat posed by xenobiotic chemicals, this article discusses recent developments and current trends.

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INTRODUCTION

A complex cocktail of xenobiotics has poisoned the global environment during the industrial revolution and urbanization age, posing a serious threat to the ecosystem everywhere [1,2]. The long-term persistence and slow or nonexistent biodegradation in ecosystems of xenobiotic contaminants, such as azodyes, phenolics, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), halogenated compounds, pesticides, nitroaromatic compounds, triazines, and chlorinated compounds, have a negative impact on the environment [3-5]. After xenobiotics are released into the environment, they go up the food chain and impair both human and animal health at every trophic level. Public interest in the bioaccumulation of xenobiotic compounds was piqued in the 1960s by the finding of methyl mercury deposits in fish and wildlife, as well as DDT (dichloro-diphenyl-trichloroethane) [6–10].

Furthermore, all species are susceptible to the teratogenic, carcinogenic, mutagenic, and toxic impacts of these contaminants. It is therefore essential to remove harmful, non-biodegradable xenobiotics from the environment [11,12]. Physical and chemical techniques like coagulation, filtration, adsorption, chemical precipitation, electrolysis, and ozonation have been used to break down these xenobiotic substances. It is not always economical, though, for a variety of reasons, including a lack of space, difficult processes, strict regulations imposed on decontamination by different nations, unhappiness among the public, problems with waste disposal, and poisonous byproducts that become more dangerous than the original substances [13, 14].

Microbial-assisted degradation of xenobiotic pollutants, or bioremediation, has developed over the last few decades into the most efficient, economical, and environmentally benign way to get rid of these harmful toxins. Using an all-encompassing activity of microorganisms, bioremediation is a technique that involves the destruction, eradication, immobilization, or purification of various chemical waste and other hazardous compounds from the environment. Technologies connected to bioremediation include landfarming, composting, rhizofiltration, bioaugmentation, biostimulation, and phytoremediation. This approach, which is now gaining traction, makes use of the metabolic powers of microorganisms to get rid of pollutants, which makes them the most suitable and promising. Using microbial enzymes to remove persistent organic pollutants (POPs) is creative, economical, and environmentally benign [15,16].

A growing emphasis is being placed on removing xenobiotics from the environment in a way that is viable and acceptable from an economic, environmental, and social standpoint, while also preventing the accumulation of other toxic components in nature. Numerous laws and regulations have been developed to address the issues surrounding xenobiotics, and numerous patents have been adopted and are in use in the EU and worldwide [17].

Additionally, patents are a reliable measure of inventive activity, and using them to analyze xenobiotics and other harmful products could benefit scientists, stakeholders (technologists, business leaders, attorneys), legislators, and researchers by giving them access to the latest technological developments, enabling them to create new products and processes, plan future research initiatives, and make crucial decisions about R&D investment plans that will lead to more substantial growth in the economy and environment [18]. Through the use of diverse omics methods, this study seeks to disseminate current knowledge on recently discovered catabolic genes for xenobiotic contaminants. This review also summarizes several patents that have been filed for the transformation of xenobiotics from different settings and provides a brief note on the function of microbial enzymes in the detoxification of xenobiotics.

Xenobiotic pollution and its impact on the environment

Environmental contamination by xenobiotics is a major global health hazard brought on by human activities including population growth and urbanization. The massive amounts of toxic chemicals discharged into the atmosphere contaminate entire ecosystems. Soil, sediment, and water include notable materials such polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), heavy metal ions, fertilizers, insecticides, and oil derivatives [4].

Scientific and technological advancements led to overuse of resources during the Industrial Revolution, destroying a number of ecosystems [19]. Unreasonable usage of pharmaceutical waste, human, and veterinary medications is another well-known source of environmental contamination. In contrast to other chemicals, medications may have an effect on aquatic life. Nonetheless, it is thought that there is very little chance of acute environmental damage from medications. While the situation may be different for long-term impacts, there is a significant lack of data regarding long-term effects and their toxicity.

Furthermore, even though many aquatic species are exposed to toxins throughout their lives, there is little to no evidence of effects for the life cycle that span multiple generations [20]. The environment, plants, animals, and people are all at risk from major xenobiotic substances (Table 1 and Figure 1).

Figure 1.

Table 1 Major xenobiotic compounds and their effects.

Xenobiotic Compounds.	Possible Effects	Consequences Observed	References
Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) PCB-156,180,194	Pediatric neurological disorder	Wide range of neural abnormalities i.e., Abnormal reflexes and neural tissue damage	[21,22]
Halocarbons CFCs, H(C)FCs, CH ₃ CCl ₃ , CCl ₄ , CFC-12 HFC-134a	Global warming and climate change	Loss of biodiversity and habitat destruction	[23,24]
Synthetic polymers	Accumulation of PVC and PP products	Alteration in the food chain and food webs, aquatic and soil pollution	[25,26]
Pharmaceuticals Analgesics, Antibiotics, Antiepileptic, Antiseptics, Beta-blocker, estrogenic drugs	Cellular and tissue damage	Adverse effect on the reproductive potential of aquatic, terrestrial and arboreal animals, Lethal effect on scavengers	[27]
Polycyclic Aromatic hydrocarbons PAHs	Aquatic and avian ecosystem toxicity	Genotoxicity, oxidative stress, immunosuppression and hormonal disorders	[28]
Polybrominated biphenyls PBBs	Adverse effects on hormone T3 and T4 secretion	Disorders of the thyroid gland and related hormones	[29]
Pesticides Herbicides, Fungicides and Insecticides	Biomagnification and bioaccumulation hazards	Endocrinal anomalies, embryonic cell toxicity in aquatic animals	[30]
Heavy metals	Nephrotoxicity, hepatotoxicity, contamination of water tables, aquatic water	Metabolic disorder, cellular and organ damage and a variety of carcinogenic effects	[31]

Impact of Xenobiotics on Soil

The main threat to the soil ecosystems of developed countries is posed by xenobiotics such as dioxins, 1,1,1-trichloro-2,2-bis (4-chlorophenyl) ethane (DDT), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), chlordane, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and nitroaromatics. Nevertheless, some additional pollutants, particularly in the soil ecosystem, have been reported to be xenobiotics, including benzene, nitrobenzene, toluene, xylene, aniline, ethylbenzene, trinitrotoluene/dibenzofurans, and chlorinated solvents [32]. Cosmetics and personal hygiene products also contribute as xenobiotic pollutants, particularly azodyes in soil due to one or more aromatic rings and azo linkages [34] and parabens in soil and air [33].

Industrial processes, the burning of fuel, military operations, the application of pesticides and fertilizers, and the alteration of soil through high-yield agriculture methods that have unfavorable consequences are examples of anthropogenic activities that drive these chemical compounds in soil [35, 36]. Soil organic matter (SOM) has a significant impact on the bioavailability and dispersion of xenobiotics in soil, as do the chemical properties of the xenobiotics and the site circumstances [37].

Chemicals used for crop protection and management, including herbicides, insecticides, fungicides, algacides, bactericides, and others, are known as pesticides and have been the most extensively utilized environmental poisons for the past century. Global production and distribution of pesticides amount to millions of tons annually [38].

Persistent organic pollutants (POPs) in soil are drastically affected by environmental conditions as moisture, pH, and temperature. Binding xenobiotic substances to soil organic matter (SOM) is one such tactic. Humification typically makes use of xenobiotics and their degradation derivatives, many of which resemble humic antecedents. It has been proposed that soil-based environmental pollutants are neutralized by this naturally occurring mechanism. Inorganic minerals are important in the transformation of xenobiotics and have good interactions with them [39].

Impact of Xenobiotics on Water

In urban regions, surface and groundwater are contaminated by the diffusive and point contributions of human activities such as urban industrial production, transportation, building construction, and habitation. Many types of research have been conducted on the presence of chemicals and markers of human activity in urban water systems [40]. Certain popular xenobiotic sensors need to be treated with municipal wastewater at sewage treatment plants before they may be released into aquatic environments. Diverse water bodies have also been shown to include a number of trace metals, xenobiotics, and synthetic organic compounds, including phthalates, pesticides, and PAHs [41].

Diverse routes can allow xenobiotic materials to get into water bodies. Airborne particulate deposition, surface water dripping from roadways and land surfaces, continual inputs from sewage and commercial effluents, as well as products from burning fossil fuels, and solid waste burning are a few of these [42]. The biological integrity of aquatic ecosystems is impacted by xenobiotic chemicals that seep into the water table [20]. Aquatic species experience oxidative stress when exposed to xenobiotic contaminants. The fish fauna of an artificial Eleyele lake in Nigeria showed a markedly elevated oxidative stress response, according to a recent study by Ibor et al. [43].

According to a study, xenobiotic substances block the antioxidant system and produce a lot of reactive oxygen species, which upset fish homeostasis and result in oxidative stress [44].

Impact of Xenobiotics on Plants

Xenobiotics affect the plant's physiological and morphological characteristics in many ways; for example, particulate matter from the automobile sector changes the photosynthetic pigments, protein, cysteine contents, leaf area, and the foliar surface of plants [45]. The extensive range of xenobiotics with diverse structures and designs causes changes in gene expression, regulation, and signal transduction in the higher plants. Xenobiotics, such as phytohormone analogs, have intrinsic interactions with plant hormone receptors and signaling pathways [46]. Metals that are needed for plant growth, such as Cu, Zn, Fe and Mo, have deleterious effects at high concentrations, but metals that are not essential for plant growth, such as Pb, Cd, Hg and As, have adverse effects even at low concentrations in plant growth [47]. Xenobiotics induce DNA damage in the case of plants due to the production of reactive oxygen species and oxidative stress. The signaling pathways get deregulated due to xenobiotic toxicity in plants by influencing various signaling receptors such as G-Protein coupled receptor and receptor tyrosine kinase [48].

Impact of Xenobiotics on Marine Life

Xenobiotics negatively impact several metabolic processes of marine animals, particularly in developing fish embryos, causing morphological and functional abnormalities, retarded growth leading to death. Altered body shape, body abnormalities, hatching delays, and death have also been recorded in fishes [49]. Dyes and paints are also considered xenobiotics because they restrict sunlight penetration and inhibit gas exchange even if they are present in the traces [50]. Pesticides and herbicides are significant sources of xenobiotic pollution in marine life. Chemicals, including organophosphorus, nitrophenols, morpholine, synthetic pyrethroids, and carbamates, are often used in agricultural and daily life; later on, these substances enter various water bodies, including the sea and ocean. Insecticide such as β -Cypermethrin is a severe threat to the life of marine life and invertebrates [51].

Impact of Xenobiotics on Terrestrial Animals

Xenobiotic exposure is also possible due to application or inoculation of pharmacologic drugs or other chemicals as part of a typical conditioning or experimental operation. The consumption pattern and disposition of xenobiotics determine their toxicity. In addition, the mechanical and chemical properties also play a vital role in determining the toxicity of these xenobiotics' compounds [52]. The xenobiotics and their metabolites may induce physiological changes in animals by altering immunological functions, cardiovascular indices, or organ systems. For example, ivermectin, a popular anthelmintic and acaricide, is harmful to some dog breeds and mouse strains due to a lack of p-glycoprotein [53]. Compared to controls, pazufloxacin and meloxicam cause oxidative damage in rabbits, including decreased glutathione content and considerable lipid peroxidation [54].

Impact of Xenobiotics on Human Health

Xenobiotics pollute the environment, so their assimilation by living species has increased dramatically in recent decades. Introducing these substances into ecosystems may increase allergic reactions, organism mortality, genetic alterations, immune system lowering, metabolic disorders, and disruptions in natural ecosystem processes [55]. Humans are exposed to a wide range of xenobiotics, such as medications and non-essential exogenous substances, throughout their lives by ingesting, breathing, dermal contact, or any other intravenous route of exposure that may represent a risk to human health [56]. Xenobiotics may alter the human gut microbiome leading to dysbiosis, which is indirectly linked to various undesirable health outcomes.

The continuing biotransformation process consistently seeks to balance the metabolic activation of xenobiotics to the detoxification of their mutagenic metabolites, as it evolved to neutralize and remove body-invading agents. When this balance is disrupted, chronic diseases and DNA damage in the human body can occur. The toxicity of xenobiotics varies significantly between individuals. These oscillations are caused by the organism's enhanced sensitivity and intraspecific variability. A large spectrum of substances is utterly foreign to the human body. These chemicals have harmful and irritating effects on various human organs and systems directly and indirectly [57].

Miscellaneous Methods Used in Detection of Xenobiotics

Appropriate extraction and analytical methods for the separation and determination of xenobiotic and derivative mixtures are critical, and they must be fast, accurate, and affordable [17]. In the recent past, there has been noticeable progress in the development of sample preparation techniques such as quick, easy, cheap, effective, rugged, and safe (QuEChERS), dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction (DLLME), focused ultrasonic solid-liquid extraction (FUSLE), solid phase extraction (SPE), solid phase microextraction (SPME), stir bar sorptive extraction (SBSE), hollow-fiber liquid phase microextraction (HFLPME) and many others [58].

QuEChERS analyzes multi-residue pesticides, antibiotics, hormones, mycotoxins, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, and persistent organic pollutants such as dioxins and polychlorinated biphenyls in food and environmental matrices. QuEChERS is paired with GC-MS or LC-MS for high selectivity, sensitivity, and specificity [59]. Solid phase extraction (SPE) encompasses preparation strategies for organic pollutants from environmental matrices. Pharmaceuticals, pesticides, carbamate, bisphenols, and phthalate acid esters are analyzed using this technique [60]. In contrast, solid-phase microextraction (SPME) allows simultaneous sampling and sample preparation and is used to analyze pesticides, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, phenols, amines, and polychlorinated bisphenols in food and environmental samples [61]. The stir bar sorptive extraction (SBSE) is used to determine pesticides, pharmaceuticals, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, phenols, alkylphenols, chlorophenols, bisphenol A and mycotoxins present in the environment and food [62].

For the analysis of lead, arsenic, medications, and other organic chemicals in clinical, biological, and environmental samples as well as petroleum products, pharmaceuticals, and food, HFLPME with a porous hollow-fiber membrane is employed. It utilizes tools for electrochemistry, chromatography, electrophoresis, and molecular and atomic spectrometry [63]. DLLME is used for metal ions including lead, selenium, and cadmium as well as chemical substances like parabens and phthalate esters. Chlorophenols, endocrine-disrupting phenols, and medications are sought for using pesticide analysis [64]. In environmental samples, FUSLE may detect organic, inorganic, and organometallic materials such as nonylphenols, PCBs, phthalate esters, and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons. Additionally, it can identify endocrine disruptors in sewage sludge, such as alkylphenols and bisphenol A [65].

Role of microorganisms in Xenobiotic degradation

Bioremediation is the technique of employing biological organisms to clean up chemical contamination. Microorganisms have a major role in the biotransformation of xenobiotics in soils, sediments, and water bodies. Enzymes and the biological processes of living things—plants, fungus, and bacteria—are used in bioremediation [66,67]. Due to their many genes, enzymes, and biodegradation routes, microorganisms possess an amazing capacity for catabolization. Many microbes have been isolated, characterized, and shown to have an excellent ability to biodegrade a variety of xenobiotic pollutants found in soil/water settings [68]. *Alcaligenes*, *Microbacterium*, *Micrococcus*, *Cellulosimicrobium*, *Aeromonas*, *Methanospirillum*, *Flavobacterium*, *Rhodococcus*, *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Trichoderma*, *Streptomyces*, *Rhodotorula*, *Candida* and *Aureobasidium* are some of the microorganisms that belong to this group.

However, only a small number of representative microbial enzymes, such as those depicted in Figure 2 and include cytochrome P450s, laccases, cellulases, phytases, proteases, and lipases, are involved in detoxifying xenobiotics. By a variety of processes, these enzymes are capable of breaking down dyes, halogenated chemicals, and aromatic hydrocarbons.

Figure 2 Microbial enzymes in xenobiotic management. This figure summarizes a few representative enzymes and their corresponding microbial sources involved in xenobiotic detoxification.

Xenobiotic Degrading Enzymes Associated with Bacteria

The remarkable ability of bacteria to proliferate quickly in vast quantities and endure unfavorable environmental circumstances is well recognized [69]. Recent genomic analyses of xenobiotic-digesting bacterial strains indicate that their evolution may have resulted from the accumulation of genes for xenobiotic degradation. The ability of bacterial species to biodegrade xenobiotics (such as DDT, lindane, PCBs, TNT, and crystal violet) has been identified through soil isolation [70].

The human intestinal microbiota has a direct xenobiotic-metabolizing potential, but it can also affect the expression of host metabolizing genes and the activity of host enzymes. Based on the examination of 16S rRNA and *gyrB* gene sequences, strain 1D of thermotolerant bacteria isolated from oil-contaminated soil at a refinery was identified as *Gordonia* sp.

Aromatic compounds (xenobiotics) act as an electron-donating substrate in the lack of oxygen (anaerobic condition), and microbes grow by oxidizing these substances in the existence of an electron acceptor. Enzymatic biodegradation begins with selecting an enzyme for a bioremediation application; it must be capable of degrading the target pollutants into less-toxic products [71]. Many bacteria species can potentially change the hazardous xenobiotic substances into less or nontoxic substances with the help of specific enzymes present inside them.

The present review aims to report recent investigations on microbial degradation of aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons. The biodegradation of different types of hydrocarbons requires distinct enzymes' due structural variation of these xenobiotic compounds at a molecular level [72]. The degradation of aliphatic hydrocarbons occurs either through monooxygenases which add single oxygen to the terminal methyl functional group or dioxygenase, which adds two oxygen atoms resulting in the peroxide formation converted to a fatty acid. The fatty acid molecule oxidizes to form TCA cycle intermediates that further metabolize to CO₂ and H₂O.

Because of their limited solubility, generation of harmful metabolites, and metabolite suppression, aromatic hydrocarbons degrade slowly [73]. Initially, dioxygenase enzymes convert these molecules to cis-dihydrodiols and then cleave them by either ortho- or meta-cleavage pathways. The fission of aromatic rings then takes place in meta-cleavage pathways next to hydroxyl groups and between hydroxyl groups in ortho-cleavage pathways, ultimately resulting in intermediates of core pathways.

CONCLUSION

By using a hybrid or integrated method to analyze the varied effects of xenobiotics and other contaminants on flora, fauna, and other ecosystems, omics approaches are a useful tool for understanding environmental toxicology and its remediation. Better knowledge of catabolic genes, degradative enzymes, and related metabolic pathways are among the benefits. Microbial communities may be crucial in mediating the effective biodegradation processes in soil and water environments polluted by xenobiotics. A range of molecular methods offer prospective ways to address the comprehensive evaluation of microbial communities at every scale, ranging from the gene to the molecule and the organism to the ecosystem. Numerous microorganisms possessing significant catabolic potential have been recognized and characterized.

Numerous enzymes, particularly those made by unculturable microorganisms, have been discovered thanks to the omics method. These creative actions have led to the discovery of some biocatalysts that are naturally suited to industrial constraints. This review has covered a number of patents that used mixed or single isolates of microorganisms to biotransform xenobiotics from polluted settings. Practical considerations must be made while evaluating resistant microbial technology, yet there is still debate on their field applicability.

To achieve remarkable breakthroughs in bioremediation, however, more research is needed to create innovative genetically engineered strains with strong catabolizing genes that can create ecosystems free of xenobiotics. Furthermore, to tackle xenobiotic contamination, careful consideration must be given to the combined strategy of green nanotechnology and microbe-mediated bioremediation. Modern technology should be used often to establish sustainable policies, which require backing from the government, decision-makers, and interested parties.

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